

Development of a metaheuristic algorithm for the logistic optimisation and reduced degradation of waste based on routes and a combined sensor

Deliverable 3.2

Submission Date: 30 June 2020

Lead Partner: FCC

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The main purpose of this document is to present the technical developments made in relation to the route optimization system that will be applied in Albano and Kozani. The route optimization system starts with the explanation of the vehicle routing problem, the document presents a quick overview of the algorithms that are able to solve that problem and finally it is focus on the specific characteristics and conditions of SCALIBUR routing system.

The vehicle routing problem for SCALIBUR and the pilot cities is focused on the degradation of the biowaste material and the on-demand collection. The sensors to measure the filling level and the emissions produced during the breakdown of the organic matter that feed the route optimization algorithm are explained and illustrated.

The document ends with the mathematical model to apply in the development of the optimize route through the metaheuristic algorithm.

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